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“KINZHAL” – A GAME-CHANGER OR A QUESTIONABLE ASSET

9-A-7660 (X-47M2 is its other common designation) “Kinzhal” is the Russian-made weapon system comprising the 9-C-7660 nuclear-capable, air-launched ballistic missile with a new guidance system designed specifically for air-to-ground operations. The missile itself is likely derived from 9M723 ground-launched short-range ballistic missile of 9K720 “Iskander” complex. Both missiles – 9-C-7660 and 9M723 – achieve hypersonic speeds through a quasi-ballistic flight trajectory without departing the atmosphere. The primary difference between “Kinzhal” and its purported predecessor is that “Kinzhal” is launched by an airborne vehicle rather than from the ground, making it less predictable, harder to intercept, and potentially more survivable than the Iskander ground system. The other benefits of an air-launch variant over ground-based missiles include greater range, deployability, and flexibility. Additionally, as it is claimed by some Russian sources, “Kinzhal” may also have antiship capabilities, although the true nature of its abilities in this regard are unclear. Perhaps its conventional anti-ship role remains desirable for the Russians and “Kinzhal” could only be used in that role via its nuclear option, or if it is fitted with an active radar seeker capable of targeting moving vessels.

Open-source reporting suggests the weapon can carry either conventional warhead with a payload of up to 480 kg or a nuclear 10-50 kt warhead. It is designed to be launched from MiG-31K fighter jets, Tu-22M3 and Tu-160 bombers and can travel at least five times the speed of sound (the definition of hypersonic). It is reported that “Kinzhal” may reach speeds of up to Mach 10 (12,350 km/hr).

“Kinzhal” was unveiled in March 2018. Four years after that, on 18 March 2022 the Russian Ministry of Defense announced that it had used the missile to destroy an underground ammunition warehouse in Delyatyn, Ivano-Frankivska Oblast (the announcement was soon followed by alleged footage of the strike), and the following day – to destroy a storage base in the Mykolaivska Oblast. According to Russian news agencies, these cases were reported to be the first uses of “Kinzhal” missiles in its invasion of Ukraine, though the system may have been previously tested in Syria in combat. However, further investigation conducted by an independent group “The War Zone” proved that Russian drone video footage of the attack on 18 March 2022 shows not Delyatyn area but a rural area close to Izum, Kharkivska Oblast. The investigation also answers the matter-of-course question as to the Russian UAV’s presence above the target area.

Following these announcements, a variety of reports emerged regarding both the validity of Russian statements and the significance of “Kinzhal”. For instance, multiple Western sources concluded, that all of those launches were mostly intended to test the weapon and send a message about Russian military expertise and capabilities rather than in order to reach significant success on the battlefield. Some analytics declared that the use of “Kinzhal” may have no strategic motivation behind it at all. Instead, it may be as much a marketing strategy

aimed at boosting Russia's military export sales by overstating the missile's capabilities and demonstrating an "impressive picture" of its practical deployment. Currently, many experts in the West say that despite Russia's claims about "Kinzhal" the significance Russia ascribes to this weapon system is exaggerated.

The Center for Strategic and International Studies (CSIS) notes, that "Russia's designation of the Kinzhal as a 'hypersonic' missile is somewhat misleading, as nearly all ballistic missiles reach hypersonic speeds... at some point during their flight." Furthermore, the United Kingdom's Ministry of Defense stated that the use of "Kinzhal" was "likely intended to detract from a lack of progress in Russia's ground campaign" and "unlikely to materially affect the outcome of Russia's campaign" in Ukraine.

Although the Kremlin has called this weapon "practically invulnerable to air defenses" and said it has no match in the West, experts has drawn mixed conclusions about whether "Kinzhal" is a cause for concern. While "Kinzhal" missile travels at hypersonic speeds, it likely is not as advanced as Russia suggests. Essentially, all missiles are hypersonic – which means they travel at least five times the speed of sound. Almost any warhead released from a rocket or any ballistic missile will reach this speed heading to its target. So, it is definitely not a brand-new technology. At the same time modern hypersonic weapons, which are being developed by technologically advanced countries fit under the category of either hypersonic glide vehicles or hypersonic cruise missiles and are designed to travel at hypersonic speed while adjusting course and altitude to fly under radar detection and around missile defenses. The air-launched ballistic "Kinzhal" definitely does not meet these criteria.

Even so, it can be mentioned that in spite of its limited maneuverability "Kinzhal" missile has all the advantages of air launch – a longer range than that of similar ground systems and the ability to attack from multiple, unpredictable directions. Additionally, the flying missile carrier might also be more survivable than the road-mobile launch system and the MiG-31's ability to reach high-speed and high-altitude prior to release gives "Kinzhal" a considerable boost in range and speed which together with the missile's capability to modify its trajectory outside of a traditional ballistic arc make its interception quite challenging. As well it is presently unknown if "Kinzhal" also packs a similar decoy-launching capability as the "Iskander-M" was recently revealed to possess, which could also help it penetrate air defenses.

Anyway "Kinzhal" together with other pieces of the vast Russian missile arsenal remains a means to demonstrate superiority in limited operational circumstances, especially when conventional airpower does not play a dominant role.

However, while "Kinzhal" is a dangerous weapon, most experts believe that it does not essentially differ from previously used armament and for sure cannot be a game-changer under present conditions. In this instance its hypersonic designation evidently has only nominal significance. Still, its use highlights the so-called hypersonic arms race, as Russia, the United States, and China continue funding research and development of this class of weapons and seeking to claim and/or demonstrate the success of those efforts.